

LASER GENERATED ULTRASONIC WAVES FOR NON DESTRUCTIVE TESTING OF COMPOSITES MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT:

Usually Non Destructive Testing of fibre reinforced composite materials are based on ultrasonics, thermal, and holographics methods. A novel technique based on elastic wave generation by thermoelastic effect has been recently investigated for contactless inspection of aircraft composite structures. An evaluation of pulsed laser sources for the generation of transient bulk elastic waves in composite materials is presented. An experimental approach has been carried out to determine the ablation threshold of carbon/epoxy material. Unlike metallic materials, the fiber reinforced composites exhibit an intrinsic anisotropy due to the carbon fiber orientation. This anisotropy, which plays an important role in the elastic waves propagation, has been experimentally shown through directivity angular diagrams, and compared with theoretical diagrams to identify a self focusing effect.

INTRODUCTION

Among Non Destructive Testing processes, ultrasonic techniques are widely used in aeronautics for the inspection of composite materials. Generally, these techniques require a coupling medium between the piezoelectric transducers and the composite part to be inspected. This is done either by local or by total immersion in water, and needs a mechanical system to maintain the transducer perpendicular to the part. In order to make easier the industrial applications, a novel technique called Laser-Ultrasonics has been recently investigated for contactless acoustic inspection of aircraft composite structures. The evaluation of pulsed laser sources for the generation of bulk waves in composite materials has been undertaken. The adaptation of laser ultrasounds to non metallic materials such as composites requires a systematic approach in order to take into account their numerous specificities. Indeed, unlike metallic materials [1,2,3], the fiber reinforced composites present an intrinsic anisotropy due to the fibers orientation and the different mechanisms of ultrasonic generation by laser are connected to optical, thermal and thermomechanical material properties. An experimental approach has been carried out:

- to determine the ablation threshold of carbon/epoxy material so to fix the boundary between the two exciting mechanisms : Thermoelastic and Ablation regimes
- to study the thermoelastic generation of acoustic waves in composite materials.

These anisotropic effects have been investigated either through the elastic wave propagation and through the directivity angular diagrams. Theoretical diagrams are compared with experimental results. The experimental results were obtained with a laser for the excitation in the thermoelastic regime and with piezoelectric transducers for the detection. The ultrasonic wave fronts generated by laser are presented and identified for two different lay up design composites. Intended to get the optimal laser parameters, a test campaign has been undertaken to estimate the influence of impact size, and incidence angle of the laser beam on the acoustic features evolution (frequency, directivity).

1.THERMOELASTICITY / ABLATION

For isotropic materials previous works [2] have shown that when a low power laser pulse strikes a solid surface, one part of the incident energy is reflected and the other part is absorbed and heat converted. The fast temperature rise, localized just below the surface, produces a thermal expansion of the material. This expansion develops a stress field since the material remains in an elastic state, and constitutes the thermoelastic source. These transient stresses give rise to forces mainly tangential to the surface and radially orientated with respect to the laser beam. In this thermoelastic regime, no damage occurs and the magnitude of the expansion increases linearly as a function of the laser energy density deposited onto the surface.

The second regime called "ablation regime" is obtained at higher surface energy density (fluence) and produces a partial surface degradation as a consequence of material vaporization. In this case, the transient forces are mainly perpendicular to the surface thus generating strong longitudinal waves. At the epicentre, the longitudinal wave magnitude follows approximatively an exponential law as the fluence increases.

Ablation threshold of composite material

The measurements of longitudinal wave magnitude as a function of the laser fluence deposited onto the surface provides a simple experimental method to determine the transition between the two exciting mechanisms. This method was applied with a composite plate (thickness 4 mm) and contact piezoelectric transducers used for detection on the opposite sample face at the epicentre. The laser used in this experiment is a pulsed Nd:YAG at 1.06 μ m.

During the fluence increase, the change of curvature of the longitudinal wave magnitude curve reveals the transition between the two different exciting regimes. This change of curvature comes from the thermoelastic linear behaviour and the quasi exponential one in the ablation regime.

The results are summed up in Table 1. For a thermoset carbon/epoxy material, measurement exploitation shows 3 key values of fluence [4].

FLUENCE (kJ/m ²)	MATERIAL BEHAVIOR
< 3.5	pure thermoelastic expansion limited by the resin discoloration at the surface.
3.5 to 7.5	intermediary regime corresponding to ablation initiation with local resin fusion.
> 7.5	ablation regime installation with resin wrenchings on the surface.

Table 1 : Classification of the carbon/epoxy composite behavior versus the laser fluence.

With this kinetical evolution, a practical ablation threshold of 5.2 kJ/m² has been evaluated for composite material manufactured with carbon fiber and thermoset epoxy resin. These results are in a good agreement with those described by Andrew from Rockwell [5] on a similar composite material.

2.COMPOSITE MATERIAL ANISOTROPY

The sensitivity of the thermoelastic phenomenon to various material properties leads us to roughly characterize the studied medium, taking into account the role of the anisotropy of laminate composite materials.

Indeed, the composite material investigated is constituted of carbon fibers embedded in epoxy resin both having highly different physical properties, especially optical, thermal and mechanical ones.

Moreover, the fiber orientation induces a strong anisotropy particularly for the thermal and mechanical properties.

The anisotropy of the physical properties is illustrated by one of the major thermoelastic parameters which is the expansion coefficient. Figure 1 reports this parameter for the three main axes of the material. The numerical values show that the expansion coefficient along the fiber direction is nearly zero, compared to $35.10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ in a fiber normal plane.

At the same time, the mechanical properties such as the stiffness constants depend strongly on the fiber direction and govern the bulk elastic wave behaviour during the acoustic propagation.

- $\alpha_1 = + 36.2 \text{ } \mu\text{m} / \text{m } ^\circ\text{C}$
- $\alpha_2 = + 33.2 \text{ } \mu\text{m} / \text{m } ^\circ\text{C}$
- $\alpha_3 = - 2.2 \text{ } \mu\text{m} / \text{m } ^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 1 : linear expansion coefficients, average values between 40 and 175°C for a CFRP.

Figure 2: Half cylindrical composite sample with machined facets

3. EXPERIMENTAL PART

Our experimental investigations were orientated through a phenomenological approach to show the consequences of these different anisotropic parameters on the ultrasonic signal.

The experimental study was restricted to the thermoelastic generation in composite materials. The aim was to determine the different kind of waves generated by a laser in composites. The waves were indentified through time-of-flight measurements. The exploitation of the angular magnitude distribution of each wave provided the angular directivity pattern in the far field.

The signal analysis and the directivity patterns revealed the anisotropy effects on the coupled generation and propagation phenomenons in the composite material.

3.1. Measurement method

The measurements were carried out on two different lay-up samples; the first one has an unidirectional stacking (the fibers are all aligned in the same direction), the second one a cross ply stacking sequence $0^\circ; +45^\circ; 90^\circ; -45^\circ$. For each of these configurations, the samples were machined and cut in order to have a half cylindrical form of 50mm in radius with 16 facets on the convex surface. These 16 facets (all 10° distributed) were used as measurement planes to ensure a correct coupling between the test sample and the 2.25 MHz piezoelectric transducers used for detection (Fig.2).

The thermoelastic generation was achieved with a dye pulsed laser having a 590nm wavelength and a pulse width of 2.2 μs .

After photothermal excitation at the center of the sample plane face, the acoustic signals were amplified, displayed, and recorded on a digital oscilloscope. The angular directivity patterns were obtained by measuring the peak-to-peak magnitude of each recorded acoustic waves in terms of the detection angle.

3.2. Results and discussion

For each of the two samples (two different stackings) recording series have been made with three piezoelectric transducer types:

- longitudinal wave (polarization // to propagation)
- shear wave (polarization type 2 \perp to propagation)
- shear wave (polarization type 3 \perp to propagation)

The type 2 squares with the polarization direction perpendicular to the first ply fiber orientation. The type 3 squares with the fiber direction (see orientation marks in Fig.2).

Figure 3 : Laser ultrasonic echograms obtained with an unidirectional sample.

Figure 4: Laser ultrasonic echograms obtained with a cross ply sample.

3.2.1 Unidirectional composite lay up

For each of the three detection modes, the echograms obtained at each observation angles between -75° and $+75^\circ$ are reported in Fig.3a, 3b and 3c (1 signal each 10 degrees). These results show that in this material, three separate waves are generated at the same time in the thermoelastic regime : one longitudinal wave and two quasi-shear waves, including the slow one (type 2 polarization) and the fast one (type 3 polarization).

Whatever the observation angle is, each of these three waves presents the same time of arrival. From an acoustic point of view, the plane perpendicular to the fiber direction could be considered as an isotropic propagation plane.

Otherwise, anisotropy must be taken into account when we compare the relative magnitude of the two orthogonally polarized shear waves. As a matter of fact, the slowest quasi-shear wave (type 2 polarization) provides a magnitude five times greater than the faster quasi-shear wave (type 3 polarization) does. This result gives a clear indication of the fiber orientation and it shows the important role of the expansion coefficient anisotropy previously described.

Figure 4 shows the angular directivity patterns associated to the longitudinal and slowest shear waves. For longitudinal wave (Fig.4a), it appears two symmetrical lobes orientated to $+65^\circ$ et -65° . For shear wave, two main lobes are orientated to $+25^\circ$ and -25° and two secondary lobes appear at $+65^\circ$ and -65° . These directivity patterns obtained in a plane perpendicular to the fiber direction are very closed to those obtained with aluminum [2]. But at the epicenter (0°) the longitudinal wave magnitude does not vanished for composite materials.

Figure n°4 : Experimental directivity patterns for unidirectional stacking in the 1-2 plane. a) longitudinal wave. b) shear wave.

3.2.2 Cross ply composite lay up

In the case of cross ply stacking, echograms recorded for longitudinal and shear waves are reported in Fig.5a, 5b, 5c. For each wave types, the velocity change in terms of the observation angle describes the global mechanical anisotropy effect and particularly the periodic cross ply stacking role in the 1-2 plane of propagation.

To identify the acoustic wave types, a comparison between the measured wave speeds and the computed energy velocity curves has been achieved. Figure 6 shows a good agreement for longitudinal wave and quite modest one for shear wave but sufficient for an accurate identification.

Thus three main wavefronts have been identified in the 1-2 plane of the cross ply stacking: Quasi-Longitudinal (QL), Quasi-Shear (QS), and a Head Wave (HW).

Figure n°6 : Cross ply stacking : experimental wave speed (\square , $+$) and computed energy velocities ($-$) in the anisotropic plane.

Figure 7 : Experimental directivity patterns for cross ply stacking in the 1-2 plane. a) longitudinal wave. b) shear wave.

3.3 Self focusing effect in anisotropic plane of propagation

The longitudinal wave directivity pattern (Fig.7a) shows that only just one lobe appears at the epicentre. This single lobe obtained at 2.25 MHz seems to come from a "pseudo-focalization" effect connected with laminate cross ply structure.

In the same way, the lobes obtained with slowest quasi-shear wave (Fig.7b) have the maximum energy at $+25^\circ$ and -25° directions. In this frequency range (2.25MHz) these two symmetrical lobes are similar to those obtained with an unidirectional composite ($+25^\circ$), except for a smaller lobe width.

This assumption of a "pseudo-focalization" has been confirmed by a computation taking into account the anisotropic effects during propagation. Simulation has been carried out from the description of the real acoustic energy vector directions calculated from the normals to the slowness surface curve for longitudinal and shear wavefronts. According to the local shape of the slowness surface, the Poynting vector (energy vector) directions are preferentially orientated along specific direction. This means that acoustic energy density is very large in these specific directions compared to other ones.

Figure 8: Calculated energy vector directions in the 1-2 plane of propagation for the cross ply stacking. a) longitudinal wave; b) shear wave.

Figure 8 shows a normalized Poynting vector representation for longitudinal and shear waves of cross ply stacking and exhibits clearly a self focusing effect in composite materials. Comparison between these energy ray tracings and the experimental directivity patterns is acceptable enough to explain the self focusing effect in the anisotropic plane of propagation. Note that the comparison must be done with the normalized diagrams for angles comprised between 75° and $+75^\circ$ corresponding to the experimental angle domain investigation because a strong defocusing effect appears for angles superior to 75° .

In any case this phenomenon is close connected with the acoustic propagation aspect independently of the thermoelastic effect. These angular directivity patterns show the important role played by the material anisotropy on the propagation after the thermoelastic excitation.

3.4 Laser beam influency

Experimental tests have been made with an unidirectional sample in order to study the influence of the laser beam parameters such as diameter and angle of incidence. Figure 9 shows the echograms displaying temporal signals obtained with a 2mm and a 5mm diameter laser beam. The results show that if the laser beam radius decreases, the acoustic wave frequency increases in a proportionnal way.

Figure 9: Diameter influence on the temporal signal.

Figure 10: influence of the angle of incidence on directivity patterns.

In addition, complementary tests have been carried out to study the effect of the incidence angle of the laser beam on the longitudinal directivity pattern. Figure 10 shows the directivity pattern evolution in terms of the incidence angle from 0° to 70° to the surface plane of the test sample.

When the angle of incidence changes, the stress field varies according to the spatial source repartition. Consequently, as the angle increases, the beam shape changes from circular to ellipsoidal, and induces two separate acoustic sources along the elliptical axe (perpendicular to fibers direction).

This can involve diffraction effects which lead to an increase of the acoustic energy at the epicentre (0°). It is shown (Fig. 10) that when the angle of incidence rises from the normal to the surface, the two lateral lobes brought near the epicenter and a third one is created at 0° for large angle of incidence.

CONCLUSION

We have confirmed that for a thermoset carbon/epoxy composite material excited by a Nd:YAG laser, the ablation threshold is near 5.2 kJ/m². This value must not be exceeded to generate a thermoelastic regime without thermal damage occurrence.

All these experimental results show the possibility in using laser to generate simultaneously different kinds of ultrasonic waves in laminate composite materials. The results yield a certain acoustical phenomena complexity.

The reported results comparison in the 1-2 plane composite samples between the two different stackings (unidirectionnal and cross ply) reveals the large anisotropy influence on the acoustic propagation.

In the case of the cross ply stacking, a pseudo focalisation effect has been identified as a self focusing effect due to the mechanical anisotropy in the propagation plane. This complex phenomenon could be an important parameter to optimize the inspection development applied to composite materials.

All these preliminary works clearly indicated that it is through the clear understanding of the interaction mechanisms, material physical properties and particularly surface properties studies that the experimental conditions could be optimized.

In order to adapt the contactless Laser-Ultrasonics process to Non Destructive Testings, further works [9] will include the development of a detection interferometric probe.

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